

Fig supp. 1

Fig supp. 2

Fig supp. 3

Fig supp. 4

A Glyoxylate and Dicarboxylate metabolism:
NES=-1.98 p-value=0.002 p.adjust=0.037

B Pyruvate metabolism:
NES=-2.209 p-value=0.002 p.adjust=0.037

C Glutathione metabolism :
NES=-1.746 p-value=0.004 p.adjust=0.042

D Tryptophan metabolism:
NES=-1.795 p-value=0.004 p.adjust=0.051

Fig supp. 5

A Biosynthesis of unsaturated fatty acids:
NES=+1.8876 p-value=0.004 p.adjust=0.042

Core-enriched genes

B Fatty acid metabolism:
NES=+1.614 p-value=0.01 p.adjust=0.101

Core-enriched genes

C PPAR Signaling pathway:
NES=+1.63 p-value=0.009 p.adjust=0.0985

Core-enriched genes

D ABC transporters:
NES=+1.669 p-value=0.015 p.adjust=0.117

Core-enriched genes

Fig supp. 6

A

Fig supp. 7

Fig supp. 8

Figure 1B
Upper panel

Figure 1B
Middle panel

Figure 1B
Lower panel